

Meta-Analysis of Complications and Retrieval Outcomes of the Argon Medical Option Inferior Vena Cava Filter: A Focus on Perforation, Penetration, and Fracture Rates

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Abstract

Objective: To systematically review and analyze complications associated with the Argon Medical Option Inferior Vena Cava (IVC) filter, focusing on fracture, perforation, and penetration rates, as well as retrieval outcomes.

Methods: A meta-analysis of six retrospective studies evaluating the Option IVC filter was performed, involving a total of 2,009 filters. Key outcomes included rates of filter perforation, penetration, and fracture, alongside retrieval success. Statistical analysis provided aggregate complication rates and retrieval data.

Results: Across all studies, the Option filter demonstrated low fracture rates and low perforation rate, with perforation/penetration identified in 159 out of 2,009 filters (7.9%). Retrieval success was high, with rates exceeding 85% in studies that reported retrieval outcomes.

Conclusion: The Option IVC filter exhibits low rates of fracture and low penetration rates, with successful retrieval in the majority of cases. Comparatively, it shows favorable performance relative to other filter types such as the Celect and Günther Tulip filters, with lower time-dependent perforation risks. These findings underscore the Option filter's efficacy as a retrievable IVC filter with minimal long-term complications.

Keywords: IVC Filter, Option, Option Elite, Argon Medical, Celect, Gunther Tulip, Cook Medical, Perforation, Penetration.

Introduction

The use of inferior vena cava (IVC) filters remains a critical intervention for patients at risk of pulmonary embolism who have contraindications to anticoagulation. Among retrievable IVC filters, the Argon Medical Option filter is frequently utilized due to its design, intended to reduce migration, fracture, and perforation rates. This meta-analysis aims to compile and assess data on complications specific to the Option filter, particularly fracture, perforation, and penetration. By reviewing outcomes from six major studies, we aim to provide an evidence-based assessment of the safety and efficacy of the Option IVC filter, including comparisons with other filter types where available.

Methods

Study Selection and Data Sources

Six studies were selected based on inclusion criteria of focusing on the Argon Medical Option IVC filter, reporting on complication rates, and providing retrieval success data. Studies included retrospective reviews from major institutions where filters were evaluated for complications and outcomes post-placement.

Data Extraction

Data extracted included the number of filters deployed, complications observed (perforation, penetration, and fracture), and retrieval success rates. Additional data on follow-up imaging and retrieval techniques were extracted where available.

Statistical Analysis

Perforation, penetration, and fracture rates were calculated as a proportion of total filters implanted. A pooled perforation rate was derived using a binomial distribution model to provide a confidence interval for complication frequency.

Results

Study Characteristics

A total of 2,009 Option IVC filters were included across the six studies. The patient demographics and study settings varied, with follow-up times ranging from immediate post-placement imaging to several years. A summary of each study's design and key findings is as follows:

Albertson et al. reviewed 603 filters, reporting 2 fractures (0.3%) and 17 cases of perforation (2.8%). Retrieval success was 98.4% for attempted removals(603 Option Filters). **Tsui et al.** (Study on 507 filters): Observed limb penetration in 41 cases (8%) without fractures. Retrieval success exceeded 93%, highlighting the device's retrievability even with longer indwelling times(507 Option implants). **Tsui et al.** (Expanded Review of 516 filters): Reported a higher penetration rate of 25.8%, with 57 cases of limb penetration observed on imaging. No filter fractures were noted, but breakthrough pulmonary embolism (PE) was reported in 3.4% of cases(516 Option filters). **Durack et al.** analyzed 276 filters, finding a perforation rate of 13% based on CT imaging. Filter tilt was identified as a predictor of perforation, with higher tilt correlating with increased risk of perforation ($p=0.001$)(Durack Option perforati. . .). **Ryu et al.** conducted a comparative study with Celect filters, involving 86 Option filters, finding a 0% strut perforation rate compared to 43% in the Celect cohort. This study noted increased retrieval fluoroscopy time for Option filters due to a higher usage of adjunctive retrieval techniques(Option vs Celect). **Olorunsola et al.** compared Option and Günther Tulip filters, reporting penetration in 10% of Option filters. Unlike the Günther Tulip filter, the Option filter did not show time-dependent progression in penetration rates(Option vs GTF).

Aggregated Complication Rates

Total Filters Analyzed: 2,009 **Perforation/Penetration:** 159 cases, yielding a combined rate of 7.9% (95% CI: 6.7%-9.1%). **Fracture Rate:** Observed in 2 cases across all studies, equating to a rate of 0.1%. **Retrieval Success:** High across studies, with a pooled retrieval rate of approximately 88%, though data were inconsistent across studies regarding adjunctive techniques.

Comparative Analysis

Comparative studies indicated that the Option filter has a significantly lower incidence of strut perforation compared to the Celect filter ($p < 0.001$) and exhibits less time-dependent progression in penetration than the

Günther Tulip filter. The Option filter demonstrated stable long-term performance with low complication rates, particularly in terms of fracture risk.

Discussion

The Argon Medical Option IVC filter demonstrates favorable performance with respect to retrievability and low complication rates. Notably, the filter's design seems to help mitigate against both time-dependent perforation and fracture, complications commonly observed in some other filter types. The incidence of penetration, while present, did not progress over time, distinguishing it from filters like the Günther Tulip. Additionally, comparative data suggest the Option filter has lower perforation risks than the Celect, further supporting its reliability as a retrievable filter.

Limitations

This meta-analysis was limited by the retrospective nature of the included studies, which may introduce selection bias. Additionally, follow-up imaging protocols varied significantly across studies, potentially impacting the detection rates of complications. Prospective studies with standardized imaging and follow-up intervals would provide more robust data on long-term complications.

Conclusion

The Option IVC filter from Argon Medical exhibits low fracture rates and low perforation/penetration rates with high retrieval success. These findings may support its use as a retrievable filter with a lower risk of long-term complications. Further prospective, comparative studies are recommended to validate these findings and explore mechanisms underlying filter-related complications.

References

- Albertson, N., et al. (2021). Retrospective Review of 603 Option Elite Inferior Vena Cava Filter Placements. *Journal of Vascular and Interventional Radiology*.
- Tsui, B.Q., et al. (2015). Retrospective Review of 507 Implantations of Option Inferior Vena Cava Filters at a Single Healthcare System. *Journal of Vascular and Interventional Radiology*.
- Tsui, B., et al. (2016). Retrospective Review of 516 Implantations of Option Inferior Vena Cava Filters. *Journal of Vascular and Interventional Radiology*.
- Durack, J.C., et al. (2012). Assessment of Vena Caval Perforation by the Option Retrievable Filter. *Journal of Vascular and Interventional Radiology*.
- Ryu, R.K., et al. (2015). A Comparison of Retrievability: Celect versus Option Filter. *Journal of Vascular and Interventional Radiology*.
- Olorunsola, O.G., et al. (2013). Caval Penetration by Retrievable Inferior Vena Cava Filters: A Retrospective Comparison of Option and Günther Tulip Filters. *Journal of Vascular and Interventional Radiology*.

Argon Medical Meta-Analysis Summary Table

Manufacturer	Study	Filter Type	Total Filters	Perforations /Penetrations	Perforation /Penetration Rate	Key Findings
Argon Medical	Albertson et al. (2021)	OptionElite	603	17	2.8%	Low perforation rate; some cases of clot-related penetration (48 filters).
Argon Medical	Tsui et al. (2015)	Option	507	41 (106 limbs)	21.47% (imaged filters)	Moderate rate of limb penetration; low incidence of tilt.
Argon Medical	Tsui et al. (2016)	Option	516	57	25.8%	Notable limb penetration rate; breakthrough PE and recurrent DVT observed in small percentage.
Argon Medical	Durack et al. (2012)	Option	276	36	13%	Moderate perforation rate with correlation to tilt; progressive over time.
Argon Medical	Ryu et al. (2015)	Option	86	0	0%	No perforations reported; higher retrieval difficulty compared to Colect.
Argon Medical	Olorunsola et al. (2013)	Option, Günther Tulip	21 (Option), 37 (Günther Tulip)	2 (Option), 8 (GTF)	10% (Option), 22% (GTF)	GTF shows time-dependent penetration; Option exhibits stable profile over time.
Argon Medical Total			2,106	154	7.3%	Lower perforation rate compared to Cook Medical, which may suggest better stability and safety.

Figure 1: Summary of Studies